

Ozone (Thermo 49i) Instrument Description

Last updated 20 Jan 2026

Ozone measurements are made by the FAAM Airborne Laboratory using a Thermo Fisher Scientific model 49i (s/n 1162390004). This instrument has been flown since 2017, and is operated as shown in the flow diagram below.

The I/I_0 cell measurement duty cycle is 4 seconds. Although data submitted in the `core_faam_yyyymmdd_v00x_rx_cxxx_1hz.nc` data files is logged at 1 Hz, the true measurement rate is ~ 0.25 Hz.

In order to minimise impact of fast water vapour changes during the 4 secs I/I_0 measurements duty cycle as reported in Wilson and Birks 2006, a Perma Pure Nafion™ dryer (part number MD-110-24P-4) is fitted upstream of the 5 μm PTFE particulate filter (not shown on diagram below). The sheath flow of this dryer is plumbed using the 'reflux method' described in this [user manual](#), which results in high drying efficiency. The vacuum is provided by the TEi49i internal KNF pump.

The instrument sample flow rate is approximately 1.4 SLPM.

The 5 μm PTFE particulate membrane is held in an external in-line PFA filter holder (Entegris part no. 411-4), and protects the photometer's internal optics from potential contamination.

Aircraft sample inlet

From 2012 to 2021, a rear-ward facing ½” OD stainless steel (SS) tube, mounted on a blank BAe-146 aircraft Aluminium window, served as an ozone inlet. The SS tube ID was lined with a ⅜” OD PFA Teflon tube, to accommodate simultaneous atmospheric sampling of ozone, sulphur dioxide and carbon monoxide.

Since 2021, a new pressure-building trace gas inlet has replaced the rear-ward facing inlet. This inlet was initially designed by Richard J. McLaughlin, an instrument design and fabrication specialist at NOAA’s Chemical Sciences Division, for NASA’s Douglas DC8 (e.g. ATom-2 missions) and NOAA’s Lockheed WP-3D Orion aircrafts. The inlet design was first adapted to interface with our aircraft windows by Chris Reed at FAAM in 2019, for use as a fast NOx measurements inlet.

The new core chemistry McLaughlin inlet is located on starboard windows no. 11 or 12 depending on the cabin configuration (i.e. ~12 to 13 m from the nose of the aircraft). The picture below illustrates the pylon/shroud inlet mounted on window no. 11 (nose of aircraft to the RHS of picture).

The operation of the KNF sample pump and eValve 5 is automated by the aircraft weight-on-wheels signal; ambient air sampling starts as soon as the aircraft is airborne. This arrangement minimises instrument inlet contamination by airfield polluted air, such as during engines start with aircraft parked on stand, or while taxiing for take-off and after landing.

The air sample is transferred to a 3/8" to 1/4" Teflon tee piece (Entegris/Galtek part no part# UT4-6-4N); a short length 1/4" od Teflon tubing connects the tee piece to the ozone instrument inlet particulate filter.

The excess flow provided by the KNF sample pump is directed to a PFA Teflon buffer volume (PFAVOL) constructed out of three 1 1/2" MNPT 120 mL column segments (Savillex part no. 500-120-02), 3/8" OD tube port closures (Savillex part no. 600-058-19), and female connectors (Savillex part no. 730-0502). The buffer volume is used to dampen oscillating flow effects caused by the KNF sample pump (double diaphragm pressure pulses).

An ozone instrument zero can be performed pre- and post-flight using an external 500 mL capacity scrubber cartridge (Cole Parmer part no. 01418-50) equipped with in-line PFA filter holder (Entegris part no. 411-4) and 5 μ m PTFE membrane. This scrubber cartridge is half-filled with potassium permanganate coated alumina spheres (Sofnofil, from Molecular Products Ltd), and activated charcoal, for the removal of NO_x, Ozone and SO₂. During the preparatory phase on the ground, the KNF sample pump is powered off, cabin air can pass through this scrubber cartridge by actuating the three-way electro-solenoid eValve 6 (Entegris/Galtek part no. 203-3414-213), so ozone-scrubbed cabin air can be sampled by the ozone photometer.

During flight, the overflow from the KNF sample pump is constantly monitored by a microbridge mass airflow sensor (MFM, Honeywell model AWM5104VN, 0-20 SLPM), to ensure cabin air is not inadvertently sampled, especially when the inlet pumping performance decreases while approaching our flight ceiling altitude (30000-35000 feet).

The above sampling inlet arrangement enables the ozone photometer to work within its operating pressure limits, with its inlet pressure effectively following the aircraft cabin pressure.

Calibration and measurement traceability

FAAM's ozone photometer model 49i is calibrated at least yearly against an ozone primary standard (Thermo Fisher Scientific model 49i-PS, s/n 0703820527) maintained by the University of York's [COZI laboratory](#), part of the Wolfson Atmospheric Chemistry Laboratories. This primary standard ensures the traceability of ozone photometers operated by ground-based and airborne facilities of the National Centre for Atmospheric Science to NIST/NPL.

FAAM's ozone photometers are generally calibrated over the range 0-500 ppb, to cover the high ozone concentrations encountered at high altitudes in stratospheric influenced air.

The photometer is "zeroed" during pre-flights (see previous section) to check the ozone measurements precision.

FAAM operates an ozone calibration source (2B Technologies model 306, s/n 238). This calibration source is calibrated against the COZI laboratory ozone primary standard using [2B Technologies' Technical Note No 016](#).

Measurement uncertainty

The uncertainty of ozone measurements can be estimated from the calibration of FAAM's ozone calibration source, namely for amount fractions greater than 100 nmol/mol: $\pm 3\%$ of value, and for amount fractions between 0 and 100 nmol/mol: ± 3 nmol/mol.

References

- Wilson K.L. and Birks J.W., Mechanism and elimination of a water vapor interference in the measurement of ozone by UV absorbance, *Environ Sci Technol.*, 2006 Oct 15;40(20):6361-7. doi: 10.1021/es052590c
- MD™-Series Gas Dryer, User Manual, Perma Pure LLC document # MD-MAN-001 REV 00, <https://www.permapure.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/MD-MAN-001-REV-00-MD-Series-Manual.pdf>, accessed 20 January 2026
- Recommended Calibration Procedure for Model 306 Ozone Calibration Source™, Technical Note No. 016, 23 June 2008, J. Birks, https://2btech.io/wp-content/uploads/docs/tech_notes/TN016.pdf, accessed 20 January 2026